

8- Theory and D-Dimensional Multiverse

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory, an analysis of the question of dimensions can be made. By using the second representation of the main equation, describing the phenomena of "dark energy" it than becomes clear that in this framework the number of dimensions is exceeding three and aspiring to infinity. The subtle point is that those dimensions are wrapped around our own and so, imposing flatness on our own manifold and preventing it from having infinite dimensions in itself. Those predictions are made within the 8-theory which stand by herself as the only theory which combined general relativity with quantum scale particles such as gluons, W,Z bosons and electrons. Reader assumed to be familiar with the thesis, which is needed for review of this paper.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (3)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (4)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial \delta t} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is the second representation of the main equation. Notice that even though the main equation describe both Einstein theory of relativity (6) and time invariant acceleration away from extremum curvature on the manifold, it lacks providing the reason for such a process. Equation (8) is than used; our universe is wrapped in many similar, stationary manifolds, which are distinct. They are assumed topologically invariant. Such a construction than allow us to understand why each manifold can not have any number of dimensions, it is confined within many other manifolds.

Its also more reasonable to assume that there are many stationary manifolds than to assume that there is only one stationary manifold. The (8) is more elaborated equation than equation (1). Suppose that each manifold has n-dimensions.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \rightarrow N_D^{S^1} \quad (9)$$

Take into account the number of manifolds wrapping our manifold making its matric accelerate outward and add those dimensions

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial L}{\partial s(n)} \frac{\partial s(n)}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \rightarrow \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} N_D^{S(n)} \quad (10)$$

So the amount of dimensions in our framework is:

$$N_D^{S^1} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} N_D^{S(n)} = T_D \quad (11)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)